

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 08.04.2017 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Ravi Bhaskar	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Haritha Chandran	Member
7. Mr. Binoy K Kuriakose	Member
8. Mr. Anson Jose	Member
9. Ms. Alphonsa	Member
10. Dr. Sathyajith Karanth	Member
11. Dr. Vishnu Prabhu	Member
12. Mrs. Anitha D'Souza	Member
13. Ms. Laveena D'Souza	Member
14. Dr. Ravindran	Member
15. Ms. Swathi D	External Member
16. Mr. Devaseelan S	External Member

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approval of New Committee of BOS.
2. Approval of new programs in Allied Health Science.
3. Commencement of all the Allied Health Courses of the Academic Year 2017-18.
4. Finalize the Syllabi of Courses of Allied Health Sciences.
5. Approval of Infrastructure required for each Departments of Allied Health Science Courses.
6. Approval of Annual Pattern of Syllabus of all Allied Health Sciences.
7. Finalize Various Subject Experts for the Quality Delivery of the Curriculum.
8. Approval of Practical Based Teaching and Pedagogy.

The Vice Chancellor Dr. P S Aithal welcomed all the Board of Studies Members of the University, Introducing Dr. Ravi Bhaskar as the Chairman of BOS. Followed by the VC's welcome, Chairman Dr. Ravi Bhaskar welcomed all the Board Members, who were present for the meeting. The meeting there after deliberated on agenda, as had been approved by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 1: As per the suggestion the committee members all agreed upon the responsibilities of being in the Board and the mutual understanding among the committee.

Agenda No. 2: As per the suggestion of the BOS members the new programs were added in Allied Health Sciences from the Academic Year 2017-18 and the same was approved by the Chairman. (Reference Table 01)

Agenda No. 3: As per the suggestion of the BOS members all the Allied Health Sciences Courses will be commenced from the Academic Year 2017-18 and the same was approved by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 4: Discussion were made regarding the Syllabi of Courses of Allied Health Science. It was finalized and approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 5: Further discussion were made regarding the Infrastructural needs for the different Departments of Allied Health Sciences Courses. The Decisions were made and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

Agenda No. 6: To follow the annual pattern of Syllabus of all Allied Health Courses for the Academic Year 2017, as followed according to the UGC norms and up to the standards of Higher education. It was approved by the BOS as suggested.

Agenda No. 7: To discuss and finalize the various subject experts to teach the respective subjects were suggested by all the members for the Quality delivery of the Curriculum. The matter was approved by the BOS as recommended.

Agenda No. 8: Suggestion was laid down regarding the Practical Based Teaching and Pedagogy. The Chairman Dr. Ravi Bhaskar, kept for open discussion and further will be considered in the next BOS meeting.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Dr. Sukesh, Member, Board of Studies.

Dr. Ravi Bhaskar,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Table 01

Sl. No.	Programs Started
1.	B.Sc. Cardio Vascular Technology
2.	B.Sc. Renal Dialysis Technology
3.	B.Sc. Respiratory Care Technology
4.	B.Sc. Optometry
5.	B.Sc. Perfusion Technology
6.	B.Sc. Medical Lab Technology
7.	B.Sc. Medical Imaging Technology
8.	B.Sc. Anaesthesia And Operation theatre Technology

Members present:

Dr. Ravi Bhaskar

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Pavanchand Attavar

Dr. Vishrutha K V

Ms. Haritha Chandran

Mr. Binoy K Kuriakose

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